

Rethinking the Data Gathering Techniques of Qualitative Methods for Social Sciences Research

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Abstract. This paper aims to question the qualitative methods, their techniques, and instruments of data gathering. It also aims to provide a variety of possible modifications and alternatives to keep these techniques updated with social transformations and the need for more efficient research tools, especially for challenging themes in the social sciences. The samples used in this study consist of 30 graduate and postgraduate researchers who chose qualitative methods for their end-of-study projects at various Moroccan universities. The results have revealed certain weaknesses in the practical aspects of the qualitative techniques used for data gathering, highlighting the necessity of incorporating E-technologies such as social media platforms and AI assistants to improve these techniques.

Keywords. social sciences, qualitative methods, data gathering techniques, social media, AI.

1 Introduction

Data gathering is one of the most important phases in social science research. Its goal is to collect a certain amount of information that can help the researcher approach the phenomenon they are about to analyze. The results of this data gathering need to be explained in order to make sense of any further interpretation. The field of social sciences has undergone many changes in terms of methods and paradigms related to scientific research. However, the techniques of data gathering still need to be developed for a better exploitation of the available sources. Specifically, we are referring to the instruments used for collecting data related to various social themes, which can be challenging such as social problems, religious beliefs, and attitudes.

Throughout the history of social sciences, there have been many experienced methods of data gathering that have resulted in a useful classification of instruments (direct and indirect observations, semi-directive interviews, surveys, focus groups, etc.). These instruments have been crucial in advancing research. However, they now need to be updated and readapted to fit the current social reality and cultural particularities. Therefore, it is necessary to rethink their procedures to align with the specifications of the present circumstances.

After consulting a considerable amount of social sciences research conducted by Moroccan university graduate and postgraduate students, we have noticed a tendency to

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highlight the significant difficulties faced in data gathering. This is particularly true for those who explore themes that are considered taboo or culturally intimidating, such as sexual abuse, domestic violence, addiction, and values. In these cases, researchers struggle to obtain accurate and relevant information without modifying their data gathering methods. They understandably fear that any changes to their techniques may compromise the integrity or quality of their work. The aim of this study is to question the traditional instruments used for data gathering in social sciences research and explore the possibility of rethinking them. This involves considering the available options for readapting these instruments to account for socio-cultural differences and the unique realities of the research subjects.

2 Overview on previous studies

To focus our work on qualitative methods of data gathering, we have chosen to present the results of relevant research in various domains (healthcare, teaching, social sciences). Our aim is twofold: first, to demonstrate the importance of selecting qualitative methods as an efficient research paradigm; and second, to establish the framework and subject matter of our study.

In 2023, Ugwu, Chinyere N. and Eze Val published a study that questions qualitative research and qualifies it as the one that concerns feelings, ideas, or expressions. The study targets the best tools of data collection that can serve the formulated hypotheses in a narrative form. According to the writers, the use of qualitative research in the exploratory phases of a study aims to open fresh perspectives. Gathering non-numerical data for producing insights is the main goal of the methodological paradigm of qualitative research to answer why. Hence, the article discusses approaches to qualitative research (ethnography, grounded theory, action research studies, phenomenological research, narrative research), qualitative data collection methods (observation, interviews, focus groups, surveys, secondary research), advantages and disadvantages of qualitative research, and tools for analyzing qualitative data.

The second study published in 2020, by Alexis Bazen, Frances K. Barg, and Junko Takeshita in the form of a collective article titled "Research Techniques Made Simple: An Introduction to Qualitative Research." In this article, they highlight the prominence of qualitative techniques in healthcare research, particularly in understanding perspectives, behaviors, motivations, and expectations within the healthcare system. Given that dermatology deals with diseases that significantly impact individuals' lives in a negative way, it becomes necessary for doctors and researchers in this field to master qualitative techniques and apply them to clinical practices. The researchers present and explain appropriate qualitative techniques for data gathering in medical research, such as semi-structured interviews and focus groups.

In 2016, Md Shidur Rahman published a literature review titled "The Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches and Methods in Language Testing and Assessment." The aim of this review is to discuss the advantages and disadvantages of both qualitative and quantitative research approaches in language testing and assessment. The researcher emphasizes the utility of using qualitative methods for language assessment and testing practices such as eliciting, designing, administering, interpreting assessments. They also highlight their efficiency in exploring test-takers' behavior, perceptions, feelings, and understanding. However, these methods have

weaknesses related to their limited sample representation and time-consuming nature. Nevertheless, according to the researcher's findings, qualitative methods dominate the context of language testing and assessment research.

The last chosen study was realised in 1999 by Shoshanna Sofaer through a scientific article titled "Qualitative Methods: What Are They and Why Use Them?" The purpose of her study is to discuss the main reasons for utilizing qualitative methods in health services and health policy research. She also provides practical descriptions of specific methods used when interpreting complex phenomena. However, it is crucial for the field of health to ensure proper use of these qualitative methods by recognizing that special training and experience are essential for their application.

All four presented studies in this section have openly expressed the utility of qualitative methods; however, their application in different domains and the efficiency of their techniques and tools are to be questioned. Hence, there is a need for deeper reflection on the practical tools used for data gathering according to the qualitative paradigm of research.

The goal of this paper doesn't only concern the application of qualitative methods but also deals with the need for a total improvement of their techniques and tools so they can fit modern themes of study in social sciences. Additionally, it aims to explore possible alternatives for insufficient modes of data gathering.

3 Methods and procedures

We have contacted 30 postgraduate Master and Doctorate researchers who utilized the qualitative method of data gathering for their projects. We conducted semi-directive interviews with these researchers to explore the challenges they encountered during the data collection process for their end-of-study projects. The researchers focused on several themes that posed difficulties, including the selection of samples, the methods adopted, the primary instruments used for data gathering, the challenges faced in finding suitable samples, the researcher's synchronization with the techniques employed, strategies for managing gaps with the subjects under investigation, the effectiveness of the instruments used, potential modifications to enhance the data gathering phase, and alternative techniques proposed to overcome weaknesses in current tools.

4 Results presentation

4.1 The choice of the appropriate samples

For the majority of the interviewed researchers, choosing the samples is one of the most challenging phases. This is due to the gap between the community considered by data collection and the researchers who claim that maintaining a certain distance from the investigated subjects is necessary to protect themselves from subjectivity. It serves as an example of how scientific ethics can hinder familiarity with the field of study and its components, especially when observational techniques are not efficient or sufficient for gaining insight on the subject.

Researchers must be equipped with a variety of tools that allow them to expand their studies and cover all available variables. However, the inflexibility of current techniques becomes a methodical obstacle when there is a lack of compatibility between the field

investigation tool and chosen samples (such as victims of violence, sick people, persons with special needs, abandoned children, addicts).

4.2 The adopted methods

Qualitative methods are used when studying phenomena based on variable quality. They offer various tools such as participatory observation, interviews, and investigations. These techniques have proven useful in gathering data for decades. However, interviewees argue that social transformations require adjustments and additional complementary data gathering tools, especially for themes related to social and religious values or alternative medical practices.

The observed transformations in modern society have led to the emergence of individual values like selfhood, pragmatism, and rationality. These values make studying human and social sciences more challenging for researchers who rely solely on static data gathering instruments. Individuals now live according to a modern style where virtual interaction surpasses real-life interaction. For example, ordinary people cannot afford to be interviewed for two hours and answer prearranged questions according to a classic guideline.

Interviewed researchers emphasize the necessity of abandoning such sterile data gathering techniques and seeking more sophisticated ones that can better suit participants' needs and encourage their involvement in discussions about various themes.

4.3 The main instruments used for Data gathering

We have mentioned that the most commonly used instruments in this field of study are observation, semi-directive interviews, and complementary investigations. The responses from the interviewed community have shown that the majority of researchers are dissatisfied with the techniques they have chosen for data gathering. The main reason for this dissatisfaction is that the samples they investigated were not cooperative enough in providing high-quality data. The researchers blame themselves for not being able to elicit the targeted data from the field of study due to various reasons such as lack of understanding, cognitive gap, ambiguity of questions, time management, handling difficulties related to cultural differences and sample specificities.

The interviewed individuals have also emphasized that observing individuals and their behavior is no longer considered an efficient technique due to changes observed in their samples. Nowadays, individuals spend most of their time in the virtual sphere where they interact and plan their daily lives and social circles. The traditional method of observing individuals in real life is becoming increasingly ineffective for researchers to collect the necessary data.

4.4 The faced difficulties in finding the suitable samples

When dealing with sensitive subjects, researchers must be vigilant in selecting appropriate samples that can provide insights into the targeted phenomenon and its components. The interviewed community of researchers revealed several difficulties in this regard. Firstly, there is a lack of financial support to obtain a sufficient number of samples, especially when dealing with victims of specific behaviors or subjects related to social taboos. Secondly, researchers often lack training to handle fragile subjects who require special treatment. Thirdly, insufficient knowledge about the field and its characteristics hinders

establishing connections with suitable individuals for data gathering.

All these difficulties are not solely related to the limitations of data gathering instruments but also to the researchers themselves and research policies in the country. The interviewed participants argue that researchers must seek innovative alternatives to overcome these challenges associated with fieldwork and finding suitable samples. Regarding research policy, they believe it should prioritize enhancing financial support and providing professional training for researchers before they engage in fieldwork.

Around 80% of the interviewed community expressed a need for more innovative techniques to assist researchers throughout their work in the field. They highlighted the importance of utilizing new technologies as a means to connect with subjects and obtain high-quality data. Given that social media applications are widely used nowadays, they can be effectively exploited for data gathering if researchers can adapt them appropriately as trusted instruments.

4.5 The synchronization of the researcher with the used techniques

The synchronization of the researcher is the act of immersing oneself in the research and its context. The researcher must be familiar enough with the field and the individuals they are about to observe, interact with, or interview. If the observed or interviewed person does not feel comfortable during the discussion, crucial data may be omitted. Synchronization reduces the gap between the two interlocutors, making them more familiar with each other. Unfortunately, this technique is often neglected by researchers who struggle to collect data from a community that excludes them due to differences in appearance and a lack of effort to integrate into the group they are investigating. Only 20% of the interviewed academic community mentioned synchronization in their answers, indicating a lack of training and mentoring in Moroccan universities, particularly for subjects where appearance, body language, and gestures are crucial in establishing a secure and comfortable atmosphere for interviewees to express themselves fluently without fear of judgment or intimidation.

4.6 Modes of managing the gaps with the investigated subjects

Gaps occur when researchers do not make enough effort to bridge disparities with members of their sample. Dealing with individuals from diverse social backgrounds, beliefs, educational levels, and mindsets poses a challenge for researchers. Roughly 75% of the interviewed academic community admitted wasting significant amounts of time trying to adjust their language or formulate questions that are easier for sample members to understand and respond to. Researchers also highlight the impact of data gathering tools on this gap; 65% opt for using a field assistant as an icebreaker to help manage this gap by intervening in discussions and creating a friendlier atmosphere. However, 35% believe it is necessary to explore more effective techniques for establishing a comfortable ambiance during interviews.

Among the notable findings is that 80% of interviewed researchers mentioned that their sample subjects appear more comfortable in virtual conversations than during face-to-face interviews. Virtual modes of interaction could be an efficient alternative for researchers to avoid certain problems associated with external factors while allowing for deeper conversations that enable interviewees to develop their thoughts further...

4.7 The utility of the used instruments

Sticking to the old, predefined qualitative techniques in the age of technological advancement would be a terrible mistake for the community of researchers. The evolution of society must be accompanied by a scientific revolution in terms of academic research. Quantitative methods have greatly benefited from this advancement through the development of new software applications for data gathering and interpretation.

According to the majority of the interviewed community, this factual truth should inspire our creativity to improve qualitative methods and their techniques so that they can be easier to use and more effective. The need to develop qualitative techniques is now a necessity, considering the insufficiency of research dedicated to social phenomena. Researchers find it difficult to deal with social problems using classic instruments of data gathering. Face-to-face interviews seem more challenging to perform in modern society, where virtual interaction overtakes social interaction.

The technique of observation has also shown its inefficiency in investigating the field, as social interaction continues to be reoriented towards the virtual universe. Investigations are also affected by this digital trend and have demonstrated their inability to provide researchers with a pertinent view of the field and its components.

4.8 The possible modifications and alternatives

90% of the interviewed academic community believes that any modification of current data gathering techniques in social sciences research should aim at improving their use by involving the virtual dimension in their operation. This can only happen by allowing the integration of social media platforms as recognized sources of data gathering and introducing their usage in the code of ethics to protect researchers and validate their methods. According to academics who defend this idea, the need for such modifications is no longer a choice but rather a necessity to enhance academic research and keep it updated with social reality, which is dominated by technological advancements, particularly in terms of human interaction and social connections.

To address the limitations of current tools, many academic researchers interviewed have emphasized the need to reconsider existing methods and techniques in order to meet the demands of modern society. They have also suggested incorporating tools and techniques from other disciplines that can be adapted to fit scientific paradigms. Additionally, researchers must adopt a more diverse and dynamic role, moving away from the traditional experimental model towards a new paradigm that utilizes new technologies for data gathering and promotes cross-disciplinary data management.

This means that certain databases, such as medical patient records and national civic records, should be partially shared with the academic community for scientific purposes. By doing so, data gathering can achieve better representation through a wider range of samples. Furthermore, there is an ongoing need to develop new technological gadgets and electronic platforms for data gathering, similar to reference managers and other software that assist researchers in their theoretical work. The majority of interviewed academics believe that these tools can be implemented if we embrace the idea of aligning scientific research with contemporary society.

5 Findings discussion

The results obtained from this study can be interpreted at two levels. Firstly, researchers expressed dissatisfaction with current quantitative tools and techniques for data gathering, particularly when dealing with complex topics. Secondly, there is a clear need for both updating existing tools and creating new supplementary techniques based on emerging technologies in order to enhance academic research procedures in the field of social sciences.

To facilitate discussion on these findings, this section will be divided into two interpretative levels. Pertinent and practical examples from the field of social sciences will also be provided.

5.1 How to improve the actual tools and techniques

The totality of the investigated researchers has expressed scientific reservations about the current tools and techniques used for data gathering. These methods are considered limited and outdated, and therefore, a complete reconsideration of the means and procedures is highly recommended. The field should be treated as an open laboratory, requiring the development of certain competencies before gaining access.

Researchers face increasing difficulties in finding and connecting with relevant subjects for their samples due to social closeness, which is becoming more prevalent in modern society as a result of its fusion with virtual modes of communication. Meeting individuals within their social and professional spheres has become more challenging due to their involvement in the virtual world. In this regard, researchers must utilize innovative techniques and tools to contact individuals and convince them to cooperate for the advancement of scientific research. To achieve this, researchers must make personal efforts to obtain targeted results.

To address the challenges posed by modern society and its patterns, qualitative methods need to be eclectic and open to other fields and professional domains. For example, researchers can adopt a journalistic model of investigation to access their field and stimulate discussions during directive or semi-directive interviews. The mode of animation in focus groups should be engaging for participants. This means that researchers need to draw from techniques used in business shows, TV reporters, entertainment programs, and talk-shows. These creative modes keep interlocutors involved and interested in contributing to the discussion topic.

Accessing individuals' virtual lives can also be an effective approach when dealing with changes in modern life and difficulties related to data gathering when individual testimonies and real experiences are necessary for the study. Social networks offer a significant opportunity to virtually connect with individuals who may be difficult to meet in person. Group chats on various social platforms are organized by themes, ages, and concerns. Researchers can create an ordinary account within these group chats to interact with the targeted community of users. This allows researchers to build strong relationships with users, establishing trust and mutual understanding before requesting face-to-face conversations. Users are more likely to accept such requests because they perceive genuine concern from the researcher who demonstrates a great deal of interest.

Virtual interviews are another efficient technique, especially for distant samples. The same procedure mentioned earlier can benefit researchers in obtaining high-quality data by creating social virtual contacts with targeted profiles and then asking them to share their knowledge and personal experiences through audio-visual conversations or written chats. These techniques can be implemented on various virtual networks using popular applications such as "Facebook", "Twitter" (referred here as "X"), "Instagram", "Telegram", "WhatsApp", "TikTok", "Likee", among others. These freely accessible applications have a significant impact on scientific research due to their widespread usage worldwide.

The application of these new "hybrid techniques" should be taken into account by the academic board. They are an example of how a researcher can address the challenges and complexities of data gathering in their field of study. These techniques need to be validated and considered as new tools and techniques for the modern age.

5.2 The proposed possible alternatives for Data Gathering tools

In this study, most of the investigated postgraduates opted for one or more of these techniques during a specific phase of their research. However, they did not receive the necessary approval from their supervisors to recognize these methods as valid tools and techniques. Before discussing possible alternative approaches, it is important to emphasize that improving the scientific domain should be a priority not only for researchers but also for the government. This can be achieved by establishing more flexible policies for scientific research and its components.

We have previously mentioned the usefulness of partially sharing medical and civic databases with the academic board to simplify data gathering procedures. This would allow researchers to access necessary data and select a more relevant sample for their research without compromising privacy, as access would be controlled and limited.

Regarding alternative data gathering techniques and tools, there is a strong need to utilize new-age e-technologies. One main level is integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) in data gathering and classification. AI has proven its utility in various scientific domains by assisting researchers in different phases of study elaboration, such as generating written content, interpreting results, classifying references, gathering electronic sources, and checking plagiarism. If AI can access medical and civic databases, it can establish connections between given sample descriptions and matching profiles, resulting in significant time and labor savings. Proper utilization of AI in data management can create a valuable tool.

AI is a flexible technology with many extensions and forms. It can be integrated into websites or desktop applications as an assistant or developed as interactive robots capable of providing relevant statistics based on accessed databases. This advantage would greatly assist researchers in targeting sample relevance and interpreting results. The current digital trend emphasizes the integration of AI into various scientific domains, including social sciences. Innovative tools based on new e-technologies are needed to enhance human and social methods.

Overall, incorporating hybrid techniques into academic practices, establishing flexible policies for scientific research, utilizing e-technologies like AI in data gathering, classification, and interpretation will contribute to advancements in the scientific domain across various disciplines.

The second proposed alternative for data gathering techniques is creating trusted and certified virtual applications that operate according to the model of social media platforms and access their databases for scientific purposes. Designing social applications for researchers is essential in the current era, where people spend a significant amount of time on various social media platforms. These platforms can be transformed into virtual fields of study for academics who would benefit from additional features related to privacy and cooperation among research communities worldwide.

The collective database of social media platforms offers a potential alternative for researchers who face difficulties in accessing their field of study. When the subject matter is challenging, individuals find it easier to express themselves through different social network applications. Even older and illiterate individuals make use of these applications due to their simple mode of operation, which includes audiovisual and written interactions. Creating parallel social programs specifically for researchers allows them to interact with individuals through these social networks, thereby overcoming problems related to accessing their field. The goal is to design a few simple interactive social platforms exclusively for researchers while also allowing them to connect with existing ones and utilize their services (such as integrating group chats, interactive discussions, and live sessions). These parallel platforms would be controlled and limited to scientific purposes in order to prevent abusive use and foster global cooperation.

The role of social media platforms is becoming increasingly familiar in modern society, and academic communities must take this factual truth into account. Qualitative methods and techniques in the social sciences need to be reoriented in this direction to meet the current needs of academic research and address any imperfections or outdated approaches.

6 Conclusion

In a world dominated by e-technologies that influence all aspects of life, scientific methods and research paradigms must be more innovative and keep up with changes in people's attitudes and mindsets. The fact that new technologies are becoming more sophisticated and widely used by a large number of people should inspire academic research to seek new techniques and tools that assist researchers in their studies. They should also be equipped with unified and valid gadgets, tools, and procedures that enable them to make proper use of these new e-technologies.

7 Study limitations

This study focuses on the problems observed when consulting the outcomes of graduate and postgraduate academic researchers regarding the imperfections of current data gathering techniques and tools. The findings are based on semi-directive interviews conducted with 30 postgraduates (Master's and Doctorate) who have opted for qualitative methods. However, it is important to note that the results discussed in this article cannot be generalized or applied to other methods (such as quantitative ones), which require further analysis to test their data gathering techniques and tools.

9 References

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